

Bridging the gap: Examining parental involvement strategies and their impact on homework completion rates in mathematics

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Abstract:

This research examines the influence of parental involvement tactics on students' mathematics homework completion rates, aimed at pinpointing crucial factors and evaluating the efficacy of such strategies. Utilizing a qualitative-quantitative approach, including with students, parents, and teachers, the study identifies distractions, workload, family obligations, and insufficient teacher support as significant barriers to mathematics homework completion. Time management, comprehension, and fatigue also play minor roles. The findings indicate that targeted parental involvement strategies can significantly enhance completion rates, with effective methods including accessible support, designated study spaces, breaking down assignments, fostering student autonomy, and leveraging technology. Additionally, parental involvement fosters stronger parent-child relationships, boosts student confidence, and promotes a positive attitude toward mathematics. To create a conducive learning environment, schools, teachers, and parents should collaborate, implementing recommendations such as creating quiet areas, promoting digital detox initiatives, managing workload, offering targeted support, establishing study environments, and setting clear expectations for mathematics practice.

Keywords: Engagement Motivation; Mathematic homework completion; Parental involvement; Student success; Supportive environment

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Introduction

Mathematics homework is an integral part of the education system, as it promotes independent learning, reinforces concepts taught in class, and develops students' responsibility and time management skills. However, many students struggle with completing mathematical homework, which can negatively impact their academic progress and overall performance. This research was focused on exploring the effectiveness of parental involvement strategies to enhance Mathematics homework completion rates among students. Students' narratives reveal different kinds of parental

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involvement practices that are not restricted to parents who hold higher levels of education or who are familiar with the educational system. In addition, their narratives also reflected their need for encouragement and motivation, their need for practical support in everyday school life, and their appreciation of clearly expressed expectations regarding education (Schmid & Garrels, 2021). Thus, the study aimed to explore the effectiveness of parental involvement strategies in enhancing Mathematic homework completion rates among students.

Parental involvement is considered an essential factor in a child's academic success, and studies have shown that students whose parents are actively involved in their education perform better in school (Ribeiro et al., 2021). The proposed action research will identify effective parental involvement strategies that can improve Mathematic homework completion rates among students. By partnering with parents, teachers can work towards a common goal of helping students complete their Mathematical homework, which can enhance their understanding of concepts and reinforce classwork topics. revealed that there was not a significant correlation between parental involvement and student academic achievement (Otani, 2020), such as parents checking grades (Ribeiro et al., 2021; Smokoska, 2020).

Mathematics homework is a valuable component of students' learning experiences that can help reinforce critical skills and concepts taught in the classroom. However, a challenge that teachers often face is ensuring that students consistently complete their Mathematical homework assignments. This can impact students' performance in class and lead to lower academic achievement. Parental involvement can play an important role in addressing this challenge by providing support, encouragement, and resources to help students complete their coursework. By implementing strategies that promote parental involvement in the Mathematical homework process, teachers can increase the likelihood that students will complete their assignments accurately and consistently. Addressing this challenge requires the involvement of parents, who can provide support (Ribeiro et al., 2021), encouragement, and resources to help students complete their coursework. By implementing strategies that promote parental involvement in the Mathematical homework process, teachers can increase the likelihood that students will complete their assignments accurately and consistently (Lawrence & Fakuade, 2021).

Mathematic homework completion rates are influenced by factors such as the difficulty level of the assignments, the amount of Mathematic homework assigned, personal circumstances and home environment, student motivation and engagement, the teacher's role, and time management skills. By understanding and addressing these factors, educators can encourage higher completion rates among students. A study by Kong and Yasmin (2022) reveals that an authoritative parenting style is positively associated with learning outcomes among Chinese students. Moreover, the mediating role of parental self-efficacy has been tested and proved to be a potential mediator between parental style and children's learning outcomes. High PSE is linked to parents' adoption of a variety of optimum parenting practices throughout childhood, including maternal sensitivity and responsiveness to children's needs, warm and affectionate parental behavior, and monitoring. Additionally, a study (Osorio-Saez et al., 2021). Results show that parents are more engaged in children's learning when well-structured technological tools are provided or suggested by schools, and when parents are socially influenced by the opinions of other parents, teachers, children, the general public, relatives, etc. Conversely, they are less engaged when they perceive the technological tools to be challenging and beyond their knowledge or skills. The study's findings have

practical implications for governments and school leaders, who need to be aware of the factors likely to determine the use of technology at home and take action to meet parents' needs when using technology to support learning. Fitzmaurice et al. (2021) found that parents' homework practices involved providing practical, educational, and emotional support for their children.

Parental involvement is crucial for a child's academic and personal development. Some common strategies include regular communication between parents and teachers, parent-teacher conferences, and involvement in school events and activities (Ribeiro et al., 2021). These strategies are effective in improving the academic performance, social skills, and overall well-being of children. Other creative strategies include creating a parent-teacher communication app, organizing parent workshops on topics such as child development and learning strategies, and involving parents in decision-making processes within the school. The key is to find a strategy that works best for the particular school and community and to continuously evaluate and adapt these strategies for maximum effectiveness.

Researchers found that parental involvement strategies that focus on building strong relationships between parents, teachers, and students have the greatest impact on student success. This includes strategies such as regular communication, involving parents in decision-making processes, and parent workshops on topics such as child development and learning strategies (Kraft & Rogers, 2015). Parental involvement in Mathematic homework positively impacts students' academic achievement. It creates a supportive and encouraging environment, builds confidence, and motivates students. Parents provide clarification and guidance, ensuring understanding of concepts and improving performance. They also help develop time management skills and reinforce learning. Individualized attention targets specific challenges, boosting academic achievement (Otani, 2020). Furthermore, parental involvement fosters communication with teachers, enabling prompt addressing of concerns and promoting collaboration. In summary, actively engaging in their child's Mathematic homework significantly contributes to educational success (Ribeiro et al., 2021).

Autonomy support during Mathematic homework was predicted by parent mastery goal, parents' control and interference by their performance goal and perceptions of child efficacy, and cognitive engagement as supplementary to Mathematic homework by parent perceptions of child efficacy. Parental autonomy support, control, and interference were differentially associated with student mastery and performance goal orientations, whereas parent cognitive engagement was associated with student efficacy beliefs (Gonida & Cortina, 2014). Developing and implementing new parental involvement strategies involves collaboration with educators, providing education and training for parents, setting clear expectations and guidelines, integrating technology, offering individualized support, employing culturally responsive approaches, building a sense of community, and seeking feedback and evaluation. These strategies foster a supportive educational environment and enhance students' academic achievement by actively involving parents in their child's education.

Parental involvement is crucial for the success and development of children in education, so educational institutions and policymakers are constantly seeking new strategies to encourage and enhance parental involvement. However, the effectiveness of these strategies must be evaluated to ensure they have the desired impact on student outcomes. This evaluation process involves setting clear and measurable goals aligned with the desired outcomes, considering contextual factors that may influence

effectiveness, collecting both qualitative and quantitative data, conducting longitudinal studies, collaborating with stakeholders, and assessing cost-effectiveness. By implementing a comprehensive evaluation process, education stakeholders can make informed decisions for improving student outcomes (Erdem & Kaya, 2020). Paulynice (2020) examined the effects of a technology-based parental involvement program on student achievement. The researchers implemented a randomized controlled trial to assess the impact of the intervention on a sample of 500 students in two schools. The results showed that the program significantly improved student achievement in both reading and math, suggesting the effectiveness of this new parental involvement strategy.

The study conducted by Schmid and Garrels (2021) Parental involvement is positively associated with student's educational success. However, research shows that levels of involvement and participation vary considerably, depending on parents' social and economic resources. Understanding more about the kinds of involvement that matter to students themselves is important, as it may help to determine how best to support those from less advantageous backgrounds. On the other hand, the study by McClain et al (2029) conducted a randomized controlled trial to analyze the impact of a parenting program on Mathematic homework completion and academic engagement. This study is expected to provide empirical evidence regarding the effectiveness of a specific parenting program in improving Mathematic homework completion rates and academic engagement among children. The systematic literature review by Janeiro-Otero et al. (2020) explores how parental involvement in Mathematic homework influences students' Mathematic homework behaviors and academic achievement. It synthesizes findings from various studies to determine the overall impact of parental involvement on students' behaviors and academic performance. Meanwhile, Xu et al. (2020) conducted a meta-analysis to investigate the effects of parental involvement on Mathematic homework experiences, such as completion rates, among elementary students. This meta-analysis provides a comprehensive overview of existing research, examining the overall effect size of parental involvement on Mathematic homework completion rates and identifying any potential moderating factors.

Alias et al. (2023) conducted a systematic review of interventions for parental involvement for students with disabilities and their impact on Mathematic homework completion rates. The study found that interventions targeting parental involvement can effectively improve Mathematic homework completion rates for students with disabilities. McClelland et al. (2021) conducted a study that explored the influence of high-quality parent-child interactions on Mathematic homework motivation and completion rates. The study found that positive interactions between parents and children play a crucial role in motivating students to complete their Mathematic homework. Conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis on parent-based interventions for improving children's academic performance, including Mathematic homework completion rates (Allee-Herndon & Roberts, 2019; Cosso et al., 2022; Sheridan et al., 2019). The study provided a comprehensive overview of various intervention strategies and their effectiveness in improving Mathematic homework completion rates. Intervention may include digital tools utilization like math apps online and offline software (Nobis, 2021) supported (Lawrence & Fakuade, 2021). Studies have shown that programs aimed at closing the homework gap are less likely to succeed in the long run if they don't address all three aspects of digital equity (Reisdorf et al., 2019).

Existing studies have explored various parental involvement strategies like regular communication, workshops, and technology-based programs (Ribeiro et al., 2021). Moreover, research suggests that building strong relationships between parents, teachers, and students is most effective. Studies also confirm the positive impact of parental involvement on math homework completion, as shown (Alias et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2020).

However, some gaps remain. We need a deeper understanding of how students perceive and value different involvement strategies, which Schmid and Garrels (2021) partially addressed. Additionally, while research like McClelland et al. (2021) is ongoing, we require more studies on the effectiveness of specific intervention programs in improving homework completion and engagement. Finally, the influence of factors like socioeconomic background and cultural differences on the success of these strategies needs further exploration.

Objectives

This research aimed to provide evidence-based strategies that could be implemented in schools to improve Mathematic homework completion rates through the engagement of parents. Specifically, it: (1) Identified the factors that affected Mathematic homework completion rates among students; (2) Explored the existing parental involvement strategies in improving Mathematic homework completion rates; and (3) Examined the impacts of parental involvement in the Mathematic homework process on students' academic achievement. By addressing these gaps, the research aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for schools and educators to improve math homework completion rates through effective and culturally responsive parental involvement strategies.

Research Methods

This qualitative and quantitative research study was conducted during the first semester of the 2022-2023 academic year in a laboratory high school, involving junior high school students selected proportionally from the entire student population using Slovin's formula. The research design employed for the qualitative approach was an interview for the factors affecting mathematics homework completion, and for quantitative data a survey questionnaire, which underwent rigorous validation procedures to ensure its reliability and validity before being administered to a sample participants to assess existing parental involvement strategies and the impacts of parental involvement in the Mathematic homework process on students' academic achievement. Data analysis utilized frequency counts and percentages to summarize and interpret the collected data, focusing on factors affecting Mathematics homework completion rates and the effectiveness of parental involvement strategies. The findings from this study aim to contribute to evidence-based interventions and policies, ultimately enhancing students' academic success.

Research result

Factors Affecting Mathematics Homework Completion

This study investigated factors influencing students' Mathematical homework completion rates. As expected, distractions topped the list, with 88% of students

reporting issues with social media, gaming, and other activities. This highlights the growing challenge of managing digital stimuli in today's learning environment. Beyond distractions, the study identified several other significant factors: Workload: Heavy workloads from other classes can overwhelm students and hinder completion (84%). Family responsibilities: Caring for siblings, household chores, and part-time jobs can take valuable time away from Mathematic homework (80%). Teacher support: Clear instructions, feedback, and encouragement from teachers can significantly boost completion rates (80%). Time management skills: Ineffective prioritization and procrastination due to poor time management contribute to lower completion rates (28%). Subject understanding: Difficulty with the material can lead to frustration and delays (20%). Fatigue and lack of energy: Insufficient sleep, poor diet, and stress can impact motivation and completion rates (20%). These findings align with previous research, emphasizing the complex interplay between various factors and student success (Epstein & Van Voorhis, 2010). In addition, soft skill-based learning media was considered effective in fulfilling the criteria for assessing teacher activity in learning media (Umayah et al., 2023).

Addressing these factors through collaborative efforts from parents, teachers, and students can significantly improve overall Mathematic homework completion rates and ultimately academic success. Crocker and Kleitsch found out that ICT access and use across ecological domains is a significant predictor of urban youths' academic achievement in science (Crocker & Kleitsch, 2023).

Picture 1. Factors that affect Mathematic homework completion rates

Parental involvement strategies in improving homework completion rates in mathematics

Table 1 highlights three essential and readily implementable strategies for families seeking to significantly boost Mathematic homework completion rates: Be readily available for questions and provide help (4.00 mean score): This emphasizes parental presence and accessibility as a crucial factor in student success. Provide a quiet and distraction-free workspace (3.05): Creating a dedicated study environment minimizes

distractions and enhances focus. Break down large assignments into smaller chunks (3.05): This strategy tackles overwhelm and makes tasks feel more manageable.

While less essential or easily implemented than the top three, these strategies can also be impactful: Hiring a tutor (2.95): Targeted support can be valuable, but affordability and availability may be limitations. Leveraging technology (3.85): Technology offers numerous benefits, but responsible use requires parental guidance. Encouraging academic goal setting (3.70): This fosters student autonomy, but parental support is crucial for setting achievable and motivating goals (Niermann et al., 2022).

Table 1. Parental involvement strategies in improving homework completion rates in mathematics

Strategies		Mean
1.	Provide a quiet and distraction-free workspace	3.05
2.	Set up a Mathematical homework routine	3.00
3.	Be available to answer questions and provide help	4.00
4.	Break down large assignments into smaller chunks	3.05
5.	Encourage your child to take breaks	3.55
6.	Provide positive reinforcement	3.00
7.	Help your child develop good study skills	3.05
8.	Communicate with your child's teacher	3.50
9.	Help your child develop a love of learning	3.01
10.	Be patient and understanding	3.11
11.	Consider hiring a tutor	2.95
12.	Use online resources	3.60
13.	Help your child manage their stress	3.51
14.	Make Mathematic homework fun.	3.00
15.	Teach your child how to research effectively	3.01
16.	Encourage your child to be organized	3.09
17.	Help your child learn from their mistakes	3.06
18.	Celebrate your child's successes	3.60
19.	Use technology to your advantage	3.85
20.	Encourage your child to set academic goals	3.70
Overall Mean		3.28

Ultimately, the best approach is to tailor these strategies to each family's unique needs and circumstances. Research suggests additional parent-led strategies for cultivating essential skills and positive Mathematic homework habits: Creating a supportive and conducive learning environment: This includes providing a quiet space, necessary materials, and clear expectations (Epstein & Van Voorhis, 2010). Providing positive reinforcement and teaching good study skills: Encouragement, praise, and effective study habits significantly impact motivation and success (Santrock, 2020); reinforcement was effective in improving both homework completion and accuracy (). Positive outcomes include the development of technology skills, improved teaching strategies, and enhanced student habits (Nobis et al., 2023). By actively implementing these strategies, parents can become invaluable partners in their children's academic

journeys, providing the support, guidance, and skills needed to excel in school and beyond.

Impact of Parental involvement strategies in improving homework completion rates in mathematics

Table 2 highlights the substantial impact of parental involvement strategies on Mathematic homework completion rates. The most impactful strategies directly influence academic outcomes, with the highest scores for leading to higher grades and test scores (4.00), followed by improving relationships between parents and children (3.75) and increased motivation and self-confidence (3.61). While beneficial, strategies like improved critical thinking and problem-solving skills (2.50) and reduced risk of risky behaviors (2.50) received lower scores, suggesting their impact may be more indirect or long-term.

Table 2. Impact of Parental involvement strategies in improving homework completion rates in mathematics

Impact	Mean
1. Higher grades and test scores	4.00
2. Improved study habits and skills	3.50
3. Increased motivation and self-confidence	3.61
4. Reduced stress and anxiety	3.50
5. Improved attendance and behavior	3.50
6. Reduced dropout rates	3.00
7. Improved relationships between parents and children	3.75
8. Increased parental knowledge of their child's academic progress	3.01
9. Increased parental satisfaction with their child's education	3.05
10. Increased long-term academic achievement	2.90
11. Improved critical thinking and problem-solving skills	2.50
12. Improved self-efficacy	2.45
13. Improved social-emotional skills	2.60
14. Reduced risk of engaging in risky behaviors	2.50
15. Improved career readiness	3.00
Overall Mean	3.12

These findings align with existing research on the positive effects of parental Mathematic homework involvement. Studies by Jianzhong Xu, (2023 demonstrate a clear link between parental support (Niermann et al., 2022) and improved grades, attendance, and reduced dropout rates. Students with higher perceived parental help (particularly relating to autonomy support) put forth more homework effort, procrastinated less, and scored higher on mathematics achievement. Beyond academic success, parental involvement fosters stronger family bonds and personal growth in students. Open communication and collaboration during Mathematical homework can

strengthen parent-child relationships (score of 3.75), while the sense of accomplishment from completing tasks together can boost motivation and self-confidence (score of 3.61).

Remember, even small gestures of involvement can have a significant impact on your child's academic journey and overall well-being. By actively supporting their Mathematic homework efforts, you're not just helping them complete assignments, you're investing in their confidence, skills, and future success. The results showed that the lower the perceptions of support from parents when doing homework, the greater the students' use of self-handicapping strategies and the worse their behavioral engagement (less effort, less amount of homework done, more procrastination) and vice versa showed that the lower the perceptions of support from parents when doing homework, the greater the students' use of self-handicapping strategies and the worse their behavioral engagement (less effort, less amount of homework done, more procrastination) and vice versa (2023). Cui et al. (2023) found that parental involvement in emotion and behavior toward education had a positive effect on fourth-grade children's math performance. When the parenting measure was reported by students, the relation between parental involvement (Lawrence & Fakuade, 2021) and children's achievement was stronger (Kim, 2020). In contrast, other studies have shown that children's perception of parenting behaviors was negatively related to parents' perception of their involvement (Hou et al., 2020).

Discussions

Factors Affecting Mathematics Homework Completion

Many factors can affect how likely students are to complete their homework. These include a lack of motivation, difficulty understanding the material, poor time management, and a heavy workload from other classes. Additionally, distractions like social media and family responsibilities can hinder students' ability to focus on their homework. Extracurricular activities can also compete for students' time. Finally, the level of support and guidance students receive from their teachers can significantly impact their motivation and ability to complete assignments. It's important to remember that these factors can have varying effects on different students depending on their circumstances.

Parental involvement strategies in improving Mathematic homework completion rates

A table summarizing various parental involvement strategies for improving math homework completion rates reveals valuable insights. Among the most highly rated strategies are communicating with teachers, encouraging breaks, and providing positive reinforcement. These highlight the importance of collaboration, creating a supportive environment, and celebrating progress. Utilizing online resources and encouraging goal setting is also seen as valuable. Interestingly, hiring a tutor received a lower rating, possibly suggesting parents view it as less essential or dependent on individual circumstances. Overall, the table offers a helpful starting point for parents, but it's crucial to remember that the most effective strategies will vary depending on the specific child, their learning style, and family dynamics. The key is to choose a personalized combination and adapt it as needed to best support your child's learning journey.

Impact of Parental involvement strategies in improving homework completion rates in mathematics

Examining the potential benefits of parental involvement in math homework, studies revealed a range of positive impacts. Higher grades, improved study skills, and increased motivation lead the pack, suggesting a significant contribution to academic success. Beyond academics, parental involvement may also lead to reduced stress and anxiety, improved attendance, and stronger parent-child relationships. Additionally, parents can gain valuable insights into their child's progress and experience greater satisfaction with their education. While some benefits like improved critical thinking may be less directly linked, the overall picture suggests various potential benefits across academic, social-emotional, and parental domains, making active parental involvement a valuable strategy in supporting student learning.

Conclusions and Suggestions

This study examined the factors influencing students' math homework completion rates and the effectiveness of parental involvement strategies in enhancing them. Key findings reveal that distractions, workload, family responsibilities, and teacher support are the most significant factors impacting completion rates. While time management skills, subject understanding, and fatigue also play a role, their influence is less pronounced. Collaborative efforts involving schools, teachers, and parents are crucial in addressing these key factors. Schools can provide dedicated quiet spaces for math homework and promote "digital detox" initiatives. Teachers can communicate workload expectations and offer resources for managing large assignments. Parents can create dedicated study spaces at home and set clear expectations for screen time during math homework periods. Additionally, all parties can work together to develop time management strategies, improve subject understanding, and address fatigue. The study confirms that readily available parental support, dedicated workspaces, and chunking assignments into smaller tasks are the most effective and readily implementable strategies to improve math homework completion rates. While strategies fostering student autonomy and motivation, such as goal setting and technology use, might seem less essential in the short term, they can still have a positive long-term impact and should not be disregarded.

Future research could explore the long-term impact of parental involvement on student outcomes beyond homework completion, including academic performance, self-confidence, and career aspirations. This study contributes to the general public by providing evidence-based guidance on effective parental involvement strategies that can be readily implemented at home and in collaboration with schools and teachers to improve student learning and success, particularly in mathematics. By acknowledging the multifaceted nature of this issue and employing a collaborative approach that addresses both immediate needs and fosters long-term engagement, we can unlock the full potential of parental involvement in supporting students' mathematical learning journey. Remember, while completing homework is important, the ultimate goal is to create a positive learning environment that fosters a love of learning and empowers students to succeed.

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